

Predictors of Teachers' Ethical Behavior: School Ethical Climate and Teachers' Professional Moral Courage

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Abstract

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Teacher

This study aims to examine the predictive effects of school ethical climate and teachers' professional moral courage on teachers' ethical behavior. The study employed a relational (correlational) research design. The sample consisted of 323 teachers working at various levels in public schools in Kilis, Turkey, during the 2025–2026 academic year. Data were collected using the Teacher Ethical Behavior Scale, Organizational Ethical Climate Scale, and Professional Moral Courage Scale, along with a personal information form. Analyses were conducted using SPSS, including descriptive statistics, correlation analyses, and hierarchical regression. Findings indicate that teachers perceive high levels of ethical behavior and school ethical climate, while professional moral courage levels range from medium-high to high. Positive and significant relationships were found between all variables, with the strongest relationship observed between teachers' ethical behavior and professional moral courage. Hierarchical regression analysis revealed that school ethical climate alone explains 24.5% of teachers' ethical behavior, while the inclusion of professional moral courage increases the explanatory power to 45.5%. These results suggest that a positive school ethical climate supports teachers' ethical behavior, while professional moral courage plays a decisive role in translating ethical values into action. The study provides practical implications for school administrators regarding the development of ethics-based school climates and the enhancement of teachers' professional moral courage.

Öğretmenlerin Etik Davranışlarının Yordayıcıları: Okul Etik İklimi ve Öğretmenlerin Mesleki Ahlaki Cesareti

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Etik Davranış,
Ahlaki Cesaret, Etik
İklim, Öğretmen

Bu çalışma, öğretmenlerin etik davranışları üzerinde okul etik iklimi ve mesleki etik cesaretin belirleyici rolünü incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Araştırma, ilişkisel (korelasyonel) bir araştırma deseni ile yürütülmüştür. Çalışmanın örneklemini, 2025–2026 eğitim-öğretim yılında Kilis ilindeki devlet okullarında görev yapan 323 öğretmen oluşturmaktadır. Veriler, Öğretmen Etik Davranış Ölçeği, Örgütsel Etik İklim Ölçeği ve Mesleki Etik Cesaret Ölçeği ile kişisel bilgi formu aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Analizler SPSS kullanılarak tanımlayıcı istatistikler, korelasyon ve hiyerarşik regresyon analizleri ile gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bulgular, öğretmenlerin etik davranış ve okul etik iklimi algılarının yüksek, mesleki etik cesaret düzeylerinin ise orta-yüksek ile yüksek arasında olduğunu göstermektedir. Değişkenler arasında pozitif ve anlamlı ilişkiler bulunmuş olup, en güçlü ilişkinin öğretmenlerin etik davranışı ile mesleki etik cesaret arasında olduğu görülmüştür. Hiyerarşik regresyon sonuçları, okul etik ikliminin etik davranışın %24,5'ini açıklarken, mesleki etik cesaretin eklenmesiyle açıklayıcılık oranının %45,5'e yükseldiğini göstermektedir. Bu bulgular, etik bir okul ortamının öğretmenlerin etik davranışını desteklediğini ve mesleki etik cesaretin etik değerleri eyleme dönüştürmede belirleyici rol oynadığını ortaya koymaktadır. Araştırma, okul yöneticilerine etik temelli bir okul iklimi oluşturma ve öğretmenlerin mesleki etik cesaretini geliştirme konusunda öneriler sunmaktadır.

1. GİRİŞ

Ethics is a discipline that examines the moral foundations of the distinction between right and wrong, good and bad, as a set of values, principles, and standards that guide the behavior of individuals and societies. By its very nature, it aims to establish universal criteria that guide behavior in individual and social relationships, focusing on human behavior and character (Akarsu, 1979; Cevizci, 1999; Ilgaz & Bilgili, 2006). While the concept of morality exhibits a more subjective and culturally sensitive structure, ethics enables the evaluation of behaviors within a more objective and universal framework of principles. In this respect, it serves as a guide for individuals in many areas, from social life to working life, from education to management (Erdem & Altunsaray, 2016; Pelit & Güçer, 2006). The social acceptance and prestige of professions are closely related to the actions of members of the profession in line with common ethical norms. In this context, professional ethics is defined as a set of principles and rules established to protect the quality of the profession, maintain service ideals, and regulate behavior within the profession (Aydın, 2002; Kuçuradi, 2003; Şişman, 2013; Yılmaz & Altinkurt, 2009). These principles limit the personal inclinations of members of the profession. At the same time, they regulate professional relationships and ensure that the profession is practiced in accordance with universal standards (Aydın, 2002; Şentürk, 2009). Ethics in education, particularly in the teaching profession, is of central importance and has become one of the fundamental priorities of educational administration since the beginning of the twenty-first century (Gümüşeli, 2006). The teaching profession goes beyond being an activity based solely on the transfer of knowledge; it involves intense human interaction, moral responsibility, and social impact. Teachers serve as role models for students through their behavior, attitudes, values, and problem-solving approaches in the classroom (Joseph & Efran, 1993; Toprakçı, Bozpolat, & Buldur, 2010). Therefore, it is accepted that the teacher-student relationship is inherently ethical and that classrooms are not ethically neutral environments. It is emphasized that teachers' fair, equal, respectful, honest, and transparent behaviors directly affect students' moral development and the school's ethical climate (Gözütok, 1999; Sarıdaş & Yıldırım, 2019; Starratt, 2004). The professional ethics of teaching are shaped by teachers' interactions with students and colleagues, the school's educational atmosphere, educational policies, and social expectations. Values such as love, respect, justice, equality, honesty, impartiality, and professional responsibility are among universal ethical principles. It is stated that the ideal teacher profile consists of individuals who are committed to ethical values, democratic, fair, and open to lifelong learning (Carr, 2006; Çelikten, Şanal, & Yeni, 2005; Göksoy, 2022; Sockett, 1993; Yıldırım, 2018). In this context, it can be said that teachers' ethical behavior is shaped not only by individual values but also by organizational and psychological factors. The capacity to defend what is right in the face of unethical situations and to maintain ethical behavior despite possible negative consequences is closely related to teachers' levels of moral courage. In addition, the school ethical climate, defined as the shared perception of the importance of justice, trust, honesty, and ethical values in the school, is an important environmental factor that encourages or limits teachers' ethical behavior. Accordingly, this study examines the level of influence of moral courage and school ethical climate variables in predicting teachers' ethical behavior.

Professional ethical courage is defined as an individual's determination to set goals based on ethical principles within their professional role, to make a conscious effort to achieve these goals, and to implement the action they believe to be right despite possible personal, social, or organizational risks (Sekerka & Zolin, 2005; Sekerka, Bagozzi, & Charnigo, 2009; Sekerka & Godwin, 2010). In this context, moral courage is considered an applied ethical strength that involves the individual confronting fear, pressure, uncertainty, and possible sanctions to defend their core values, challenge the status quo, and stand up against unethical practices (Grant, 2002; Lachman, 2007; Pianalto, 2012). Particularly in the teaching profession, moral courage means that teachers are willing to intervene in ethically problematic situations. It also encompasses making decisions that prioritize the benefit of students and demonstrating role model behavior in this process. In this respect, moral courage is at the heart of moral education (Kidder, 2005; Klaassen, 2007; Klaassen & Maslovaty, 2010). Teachers' display of moral courage is not limited to the school context. It contributes to the spread of ethical behavior at the societal level through students. It acts as a bridge in transforming ethical values from discourse into action (Harris, 1999; Kidder, 2005). However, moral courage can entail various costs for individuals. It can bring risks such as exclusion, damage to reputation, career loss, social reaction, psychological pressure, and uncertainty (Baumert et al., 2024; Miller, 2000; Reingold & Baratz, 2020). Particularly in an organizational context, a culture of silence, group pressure, and routine unethical practices are among the significant barriers that make it difficult to demonstrate moral courage (Serrat, 2017; Yollu et al., 2024). However, it is emphasized that moral courage is not an innate trait but rather a behavior that can be learned, developed, and supported. It is stated that it can be strengthened through education, role models, social and organizational support, open communication environments, safe mechanisms, and rewards (Miller, 2000; Peterson & Seligman, 2004; Serrat,

2017). In this respect, professional moral courage increases the use of ethical power in organizations. It plays a leading role in solving ethical problems. It is considered a fundamental competency that contributes to the formation of a sustainable ethical organizational culture (Baratz & Reingold, 2010; Sekerka et al., 2009).

Teachers' ability to act in accordance with ethical principles is related not only to their level of knowledge of what is right, but also to the existence of an organizational environment where they can confidently put these truths into practice. The importance given to ethical values in schools, perceptions of justice and trust, are important contextual elements that determine how teachers behave in the face of ethical dilemmas. In this context, the ethical climate provides a critical organizational framework that supports or limits teachers' ethical behavior. Ethical climate refers to shared perceptions of acceptable and unacceptable behavior in organizations. It is also defined as an important organizational structure that guides employees in understanding and evaluating ethical dilemmas and making morally correct decisions (Akdoğan & Demirtaş, 2014; Barnett & Vaicys, 2000; Eser, 2007; Şahin & Dündar, 2011). It is stated that in organizations where the ethical climate is not sufficiently established, the sense of trust weakens. It is stated that employees' focus on work, creativity, and performance levels decline. It is emphasized that negative perceptions of the organization increase and that this negatively affects organizational efficiency (Akburak, 2019; Kılıç, 2019). Ethical climate, which reflects the ethical dimension of organizational culture, is shaped through shared values, norms, rules, and procedures within the organization rather than individual moral standards. It creates a common understanding within the organization about what behavior is appropriate and how to deal with ethical issues (Cullen, Parboteeah, & Victor, 2003; Victor & Cullen, 1988; Sağnak, 2005). In this respect, ethical climate increases employee job satisfaction, knowledge sharing, organizational commitment, psychological safety, and performance levels. It also plays a role in reducing internal organizational conflicts and crises (Carlson, 2005; Demir, 2019; Weeks, Loe, Chonko, & Wakefield, 2004; Yeşil, Mavi, & Ceylan, 2017). In the context of educational organizations, ethical climate, as one of the fundamental components of school climate, directly affects the overall atmosphere of the school. It significantly shapes teachers' professional attitudes and levels of organizational commitment. Studies have shown that ethical climate has meaningful and positive effects on teacher performance, organizational commitment, psychological well-being, and perceptions of organizational justice (Altaş & Kuzu, 2013; Kahveci, 2019; Steinberg & Garrett, 2016; Wei, 2018; Yavuz, 2022; Özen & Durkan, 2016).

Education is a fundamental social domain where individuals' academic knowledge, values, and behaviors are shaped. In this process, teachers' adherence to ethical principles directly influences students' moral development and the overall school climate. However, teachers' ethical behavior exhibits a multidimensional structure that cannot be explained solely by individual values. The organizational structure of the school, its managerial practices, and psychological characteristics are among the important factors that influence teachers' ethical decision-making and behavior. This research aims to contribute to filling an important gap in the literature by addressing moral courage and the school's ethical climate within a holistic framework to predict teachers' ethical behavior. The findings are expected to contribute to the development of ethical value-based management practices by school administrators and the creation of organizational conditions that support teachers' ethical behavior. In this respect, the research is expected to contribute to strengthening a more equitable, trust-based, and ethical school culture in educational institutions.

1.1. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between teachers' ethical behaviors, the school ethical climate, and teachers' professional moral courage. Within the scope of the study, efforts were made to identify the predictive factors affecting teachers' ethical behaviors. To this end, answers were sought to the following questions:

- ✓ What is the level of teachers' perceptions of ethical behavior, school ethical climate, and professional moral courage?
- ✓ Is there a meaningful relationship between teachers' ethical behaviors and the school ethical climate and teachers' professional moral courage?
- ✓ Do the school ethical climate and teachers' professional moral courage significantly predict teachers' ethical behaviors?

2. METHOD

In this study, a correlational research method was used to determine the relationship between teachers' ethical behaviors and the school's ethical climate and teachers' professional moral courage. Correlational research is a method that aims to examine the existence, direction, and strength of the relationship between two or more variables (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2007). In this context, teachers' ethical behaviors were considered as the dependent variable, while the school's ethical climate and teachers' professional moral courage were considered as independent variables.

2.1. Research Population and Sample

The research population consists of teachers working at different levels in public schools in Kilis province as of the 2025-2026 academic year. The sample of the study was selected using simple random sampling. In simple random sampling, each participant has an equal chance of being included in the sample, and the selection of participants is entirely random. In this context, 323 teachers constitute the sample of the study. The demographic information of the teachers participating in the study is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants: Age, Gender, and School Level Distributions

Category	Subcategory	f	%
Age	20–30 years	94	29.1
	31–40 years	79	24.5
	41–50 years	82	25.4
	51 years and above	68	21.1
Gender	Male	151	46.7
	Female	172	53.3
School Level	Elementary School	121	37.5
	Middle School	113	35.0
	High School	89	27.6

According to Table 1, teachers aged 20-30 (29.1%) constitute the largest group, followed by those aged 31-40 (24.5%) and 41-50 (25.4%). Teachers aged 51 and over have a lower representation rate of 21.1%. In terms of gender, female teachers (53.3%) are slightly more represented than male teachers (46.7%). According to school level data, the majority of teachers work at the elementary school level (37.5%), followed by middle school teachers (35.0%) and high school teachers (27.6%). These data show that the majority of teachers are between the ages of 20 and 30 and are female, and that there are more teachers at the primary school level.

2.2. Data Collection Tools

Data for the study were collected using the Professional Moral Courage Scale, Teacher Ethical Behavior Scale, Organizational Ethical Climate Scale, and Personal Information Form.

2.2.1. Professional Moral Courage Scale: The Professional Moral Courage Scale, developed by Sekerka, Bagozzi, and Charnigo (2009), was adapted to Turkish culture by Yollu, Yumuşak, and Korkmaz (2024). The scale is a 7-point Likert-type assessment tool consisting of 5 main dimensions and a total of 15 items. These dimensions are: moral reasoning, multiple values, resistance to threats, going beyond compliance, and setting moral goals. In the reliability analyses performed, the Cronbach Alpha value of the scale was calculated as 0.94. In this study, Cronbach's Alpha was found to be 0.91, and the findings indicate that the scale is a reliable measurement tool.

2.2.2. Teacher Ethical Behavior Scale: Developed by Çelebi and Akbağ (2012), the Teacher Ethical Behavior Scale is a tool designed to measure teachers' ethical behavior. The scale has a 5-point Likert-type rating system and consists of 5 basic dimensions: sense of duty, virtue, human sensitivity, professional responsibility, and moral thinking. The scale consists of a total of 26 items, and reliability analyses have calculated a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.86, indicating that the scale has high internal consistency. In this study, the Cronbach Alpha value was calculated as 0.84, and the results confirm that the scale is a reliable measurement tool.

2.2.3. Organizational Ethical Climate Scale: Developed by Cullen and Victor (1988) and updated by Cullen, Victor, and Bronson (1993), the Organizational Ethical Climate Scale was adapted into Turkish by Özen and

Durkan (2016) for use in educational organizations. The scale is a 5-point Likert-type assessment tool, containing a total of 22 items and 5 main dimensions. These dimensions can be listed as social responsibility, rule-following, self-interested benevolence, principledness, and efficiency. In the reliability analyses conducted, the Cronbach Alpha value of the scale was determined to be 0.87, while in this study, the Cronbach Alpha value was calculated as 0.89, and the findings obtained confirmed that the scale is a reliable measurement tool.

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis

The research process began with the collection of data via Google Forms. The scales used were prepared to be included in the form, and the link to the form was sent to teachers via email. Following this stage, responses were received from a total of 323 teachers. Before proceeding to the analysis of the data, outliers and multicollinearity issues were checked, and no problems were detected as a result of the reviews. In addition, a normality test was performed to determine the normality of the data distribution, and it was observed that the kurtosis and skewness values were within the ± 1 range (George & Mallery, 2010), indicating that the data were normally distributed. Descriptive statistical analyses were performed to determine teachers' perception levels regarding the research variables, and basic measures such as mean, standard deviation, and variance were calculated. Subsequently, the relationships between teacher ethical behavior, school ethical climate, and professional moral courage variables were examined using correlation analysis, and the predictive status of school ethical climate and professional moral courage variables on teachers' ethical behavior was analyzed using hierarchical regression analysis.

3. FINDINGS

Descriptive statistical data regarding the ethical behaviors of teachers participating in the study, school ethical climate, and professional moral courage variables are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics Regarding the Ethical Behaviors of Teachers Participating in the Study, School Ethical Climate, and Professional Moral Courage Variables

Variable	N	M	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Teachers' Ethical Behaviors	323	4.11	0.64	-0.09	-0.56
School Ethical Climate	323	3.99	0.60	0.01	-0.22
Professional Moral Courage	323	5.39	0.86	0.22	-0.56

According to Table 2, when the data of the teachers participating in the study (N = 323) were examined, the means of the teacher ethical behavior and school ethical climate variables were found to be 4.11 and 3.99, respectively, on a 5-point Likert scale, indicating that both variables are at a high level. The mean of the professional moral courage variable was 5.39 on a 7-point Likert scale, indicating a medium-high to high level according to the scale. These findings indicate that teachers, at both personal and professional levels, actively maintain ethical behaviors, exercise professional moral courage, and recognize the ethical climate of their schools.

The relationships between Teacher Ethical Behavior, School Ethical Climate, and Professional Moral Courage are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Relationships between Teacher Ethical Behavior, School Ethical Climate, and Professional Moral Courage

Variables	1	2	3
1. Teachers' Ethical Behaviors	1		
2. School Ethical Climate	.495**	1	
3. Professional Moral Courage	.647**	.510**	1

** p < .01

Table 3 shows that there are significant positive relationships between teachers' ethical behaviors and the school ethical climate and professional moral courage. Teachers' ethical behaviors show a moderate positive relationship with the school ethical climate ($r = .495$, $p < .01$). This indicates that a stronger school ethical climate may support teachers' ethical behaviors. Additionally, a stronger positive relationship was found

between teachers' ethical behaviors and professional moral courage ($r = .647, p < .01$). This finding shows that teachers with high professional moral courage tend to exhibit ethical behavior more clearly. Furthermore, a moderately significant positive relationship was found between school ethical climate and professional moral courage ($r = .510, p < .01$). This result suggests that a more ethical school environment may support teachers' professional moral courage. Overall, the correlation analysis shows that both school ethical climate and professional moral courage are significantly related to teachers' ethical behaviors and that both variables may play an important role in understanding ethical behaviors.

The results of the hierarchical regression analysis predicting teachers' ethical behaviors are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of Hierarchical Regression Analysis Regarding the Prediction of Teachers' Ethical Behavior

Model	Predictor Variables	B	SE _B	β	t	p
1	Constant	2.016	0.207	–	9.726	< .001
	School Ethical Climate	0.524	0.051	0.495	10.207	< .001
Model Statistics						
R = 0.495, R ² = 0.245						
F _(1,321) = 104.188, p < .001						
2	Constant	1.035	0.197	–	5.250	< .001
	School Ethical Climate	0.237	0.051	0.223	4.657	< .001
	Professional Moral Courage	0.395	0.036	0.533	11.115	< .001
Model Statistics						
R = 0.675, R ² = 0.455						
F _(2,320) = 133.750, p < .001						

Hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to examine the factors predicting teachers' ethical behavior. The analysis was first performed in Model 1 with only the school ethical climate variable, and then in Model 2 with the addition of the professional moral courage variable. Model 1 results showed that the school ethical climate significantly predicted teachers' ethical behavior ($B = 0.524, \beta = 0.495, t = 10.21, p < .001$). The explanatory power of this model was $R^2 = 0.245$, and the model was found to be generally significant ($F_{(1,321)} = 104.19, p < .001$). In other words, the school ethical climate explains 24.5% of the variance in teachers' ethical behaviors. In Model 2, the professional moral courage variable was added. The results indicate that both school ethical climate ($B = 0.237, \beta = 0.223, t = 4.66, p < .001$) and professional moral courage ($B = 0.395, \beta = 0.533, t = 11.12, p < .001$) significantly and positively predicted teachers' ethical behaviors. The explanatory power of this model is $R^2 = 0.455$ (45.5%), and the model was found to be generally meaningful ($F_{(2,320)} = 133.75, p < .001$). The increase in the model's R^2 value ($\Delta R^2 \approx 0.21$) indicates that the addition of professional moral courage significantly contributes to explaining teachers' ethical behavior. These findings reveal that school ethical climate and professional moral courage are factors that significantly predict teachers' ethical behaviors and that professional moral courage, in addition to school ethical climate, significantly increases the explanatory power of the model.

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This study examined the relationships between teachers' ethical behaviors and their perceptions of school ethical climate and professional moral courage. It also determined the predictive level of school ethical climate and professional moral courage on teachers' ethical behaviors.

Research findings indicate that teachers exhibit high levels of ethical behavior, have positive and high perceptions of the school's ethical climate, and demonstrate professional moral courage at levels ranging from medium-high to high. A review of the literature on ethical behavior reveals that numerous studies show that teachers' perceptions of ethical behavior are high (Göksoy, 2022; İskender, 2024; Yakar, 2024). Studies on the school ethical climate similarly reveal that teachers' perceptions of the ethical climate are high (Boyras, 2024; Demir, 2019; Demir & Karakuş, 2015; Demirdağ & Pınar, 2025; Pehlivanoğlu, 2024), but it is noteworthy that some studies report ethical climate perceptions at a medium-high level (Ekinci & Argon, 2023). When reviewing the literature on the professional moral courage variable, studies conducted on teachers show that moral courage is high (Yollu, 2023), while research conducted on different professional groups indicates

findings pointing to medium-high levels (Deniz Korkmaz, 2025; Şener, 2025). These results show that teachers' ethical behavior and school ethical climate perceptions are high, while their professional moral courage levels range from medium-high to high. The high level of ethical behavior and ethical climate perception indicates that teachers focus on fulfilling their professional responsibilities in line with ethical principles and on valuing justice, trust, and ethical values in their schools. The slightly more cautious level of professional moral courage suggests that teachers may be cautious in demonstrating their behavior in risky or challenging situations. Overall, the findings are consistent with studies in the literature and support the view that ethical behavior is knowledge- and value-based, while moral courage is a structure that also includes responsibility and risk-taking.

Correlation and hierarchical regression analyses revealed meaningful and positive relationships between teacher ethical behavior and both the school ethical climate and teacher moral courage. In particular, the stronger relationship between teacher moral courage and ethical behavior indicates that ethical behaviors are closely related not only to organizational conditions but also to teachers' individual moral stances. The significant relationship between the school ethical climate and teacher moral courage indicates that a school environment that values ethical values can support teachers' moral courage. Hierarchical regression analysis results show that the school ethical climate alone explains 24,5% of teacher ethical behavior, while adding teacher moral courage to the model shows that both variables together explain 45,5% of teacher ethical behavior. These findings show that teachers' moral courage is a strong predictor of ethical behavior and that the school ethical climate supports this effect in a complementary manner. In other words, while an ethical school environment supports teachers' ethical behavior, teachers' levels of moral courage emerge as a decisive factor in the implementation of this behavior.

Studies in the health field also present similar results. For example, Taraz, Loghmani, Abbaszadeh, Ahmadi, Safavibiat, and Borhani (2019) reported a meaningful and positive relationship between organizational ethical climate and moral courage. This finding shows that a more positive ethical environment increases moral courage. Similarly, a study conducted by Abou Hashish and Abdel Razek (2025) on nurses found that a positive ethical climate increases moral courage and moral resilience while reducing moral distress. Furthermore, moral resilience was seen to play a moderating role, strengthening the effects of the ethical climate on moral distress and moral courage. These findings are consistent with the results observed in our study conducted on teachers. While the school ethical climate supports teachers' ethical behaviors, teachers' moral courage plays a decisive role in putting these behaviors into practice.

Theoretical studies in the context of education also emphasize that moral courage plays a critical role in translating ethical judgments into action (Zembylas, 2024). Sekerka and Bagozzi (2007) define moral courage as the process of acting on a behavior that an individual believes to be ethically correct despite possible negative consequences, noting that this process is shaped not only by individual intentions and values but also by the ethical cues and norms provided by the organizational context. In his study with white-collar workers, Şener (2025) found meaningful and positive relationships between perceived ethical climate and moral courage. He also reported that ethical climate is positively related to ethical leadership and negatively related to moral disengagement. Similarly, Çakmak (2025), in his research on nurses, showed that there is a meaningful and positive relationship between the level of moral courage and ethical behaviors aimed at protecting patient rights, and that moral courage significantly predicts ethical behaviors.

The effect of organizational ethical climate on ethical behaviors may also vary depending on the type of climate. Wimbush and Spehard (1994) stated that employees in organizations perceive the ethical climate in different ways. According to the study, employees who perceive ethical dimensions such as care, law and principles, rules, or independence tend to exhibit more ethical behaviors than employees who perceive a climate that is only concerned with their own interests and is instrumental. This situation shows that employees' adoption of ethical norms and principles plays an important role in increasing ethical behavior. Similarly, Yağmur (2013) stated that the perception of unethical behavior is negatively related to the ethical climate of the organization and that unethical behavior is more common in negatively perceived climates. Arslan Hendekçi and Özen (2018) also reported a meaningful relationship between teachers' perception of organizational ethical climate types and their own perceptions of professional ethical behavior.

In light of all these findings, it is understood that teachers' ethical behaviors are shaped by the interaction of both organizational and individual factors. In this context, creating an ethics-based climate in schools and developing practices aimed at strengthening teachers' professional moral courage is critical for the sustainability of ethical behaviors.

Based on the research results, the following recommendations can be made:

- ✓ A participatory and transparent management approach should be adopted to strengthen the ethical climate in schools. School administrators demonstrating ethical leadership behaviors will support teachers' attitudes and behaviors based on ethical values.
- ✓ In-service training programs should be planned to develop teachers' professional moral courage. These trainings should strengthen teachers' abilities to make decisions in the face of ethical dilemmas, take responsibility, and implement ethical behavior.
- ✓ Safe and fair school environments that support the sustainability of ethical behavior should be created. A school climate where teachers can express their ethical concerns and where their ethical behavior is supported will increase the permanence of ethical behavior.

This study has some limitations. First, the fact that the data was collected through self-reporting may have led to a social desirability effect in the participants' responses. Furthermore, the cross-sectional design of the study limits the interpretation of relationships between variables within a causal framework. Finally, the fact that the study was conducted on a sample limited to a specific geographic region restricts the generalizability of the findings to different school contexts.

REFERENCES

- Abou Hashish, E. A., & Abdel Razek, N. M. F. (2025). Navigating connections: How moral resilience shapes ethical climate, distress, and courage among nurses. *SAGE Open*, 15(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440251381063>
- Akarsu, B. (1979). *Çağdaş felsefe akımları*. Milli Eğitim Bakanlığı Yayınları.
- Akbağ, M., & Celebi, N. (2012). A study to determine the ethical behaviors of teachers working in general high schools. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(2), 425-441.
- Akburak, Ş. (2019). *Özel konaklama tesislerinde algılanan etik iklimin iş tatmini ve iş performansı üzerindeki etkisi: Nevşehir ilinde bir araştırma* [Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Nevşehir Hacıbektaş Veli Üniversitesi.
- Akdoğan, A., & Demirtaş, Ö. (2014). Etik liderlik davranışlarının etik iklim üzerindeki etkisi: Örgütsel politik algılamaların aracı rolü. *Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 16(1), 107-124.
- Altaş, S. S., & Kuzu, A. (2013). Örgütsel etik, örgütsel güven ve bireysel iş performansı arasındaki ilişki: Okul öncesi öğretmenleri üzerinde bir araştırma. *Elektronik Mesleki Gelişim ve Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 1(2), 29-41.
- Altinkurt, Y., & Yılmaz, K. (2011). Öğretmen adaylarının öğretmenlerin mesleki etik dışı davranışlar ile ilgili görüşleri. *Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Journal of Education Faculty*, 1(22), 113-128.
- Arslan Hendekçi, E., & Özen, F. (2018). Algılanan örgütsel etik iklimin ilköğretim okullarında öğretmenlerin etik dışı davranışlarına etkisi (Diyarbakır merkez ilçeleri örneği). *Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 15(2), 425-450.
- Aydın, İ. (2002). *Yönetmel, mesleki ve örgütsel etik*. Pegem A Yayıncılık.
- Baratz, L., & Reingold, R. (2010). The Ideological Dilemma in Teaching Literature: Moral Conflicts in a Diversified Society: An Israeli Teacher Case Study. *Current Issues in Education*, 13(3), n3.
- Barnett, T., & Vaicys, C. (2000). The moderating effect of individuals' perceptions of ethical work climate on ethical judgments and behavioral intentions. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 27(4), 351-362.
- Baumert, A., Mentrup, F. E., Klümper, L., & Sasse, J. (2024). Personality processes of everyday moral courage. *Journal of Personality*, 92(3), 764-783. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12850>
- Boyras, F. (2024). *Öğretmenlerin okullara ilişkin etik iklim alguları ile okul yapısı etkililiği ilişkisinin incelenmesi* (Yüksek lisans tezi). Sivas Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü.

- Carlson, S. C. (2005). *Ethical leadership: Influences of ethical climate, perceived organizational support, and perceived leader integrity* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Nova Southeastern University.
- Carr, D. (2006). Professional and personal values and virtues in education and teaching. *Oxford Review of Education*, 32(2), 171–183.
- Cevizci, A. (1999). *Etiğe giriş*. Paradigma Yayıncılık.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education* (6th ed.). Routledge.
- Cullen, J. B., & Victor, B. (1988). The organizational bases of ethical work climates. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 33(1), 101–125. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392857>
- Cullen, J. B., Parboteeah, K. P., & Victor, B. (2003). The effects of ethical climates on organizational commitment: A two-study analysis. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 46(2), 127–141. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1025089819456>
- Cullen, J. B., Victor, B., & Bronson, J. W. (1989). Ethical work climate: A conceptualization and measure. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 33(1), 101–125. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392857>
- Cullen, J. B., Victor, B., & Bronson, J. W. (1993). The ethical climate questionnaire: An assessment of its development and validity. *Psychological Reports*, 73(2), 667–674. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.1993.73.2.667>
- Çakmak, S. (2025). *Hemşirelerin ahlaki cesaret düzeyleri ile hasta haklarını korumaya yönelik etik davranışları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* (Yüksek lisans tezi). Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü.
- Çelikten, M., Şanal, M., & Yeni, Y. (2005). Öğretmenlik mesleği ve özellikleri. *Erciyes Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 19(2), 207–237.
- Demir, S. (2019). Etik iklim ve okuldan ayrılma niyeti arasındaki ilişki: Örgütsel bağlılığın aracılık rolü. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 34(3), 824–838.
- Demir, S., & Karakuş, M. (2015). Etik iklim ile öğretmen ve öğrencilerin güven ve motivasyon düzeyleri arasındaki ilişki. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 21(2), 183-212.
- Demirdağ, S., & Pınar, G. (2025). Okulda Etik İklim İle Örgütsel Sinerji Arasındaki İlişki. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Buca Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, (65), 3289-3305.
- Ekinci, S., & Argon, T. (2023). Etik iklim ile öğretimsel denetime ilişkin öğretmen görüşleri. *Uluslararası Liderlik Eğitimi Dergisi*, 7(2), 14–28.
- Erdem, A. R., & Altunsaray, M. (2016). Eğitimde niteliği belirleyen önemli bir etken: Eğitim etiği. *Akademik Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 23, 21–30.
- Erdem, A. R., & Şimşek, S. (2013). Öğretmenlik meslek etiğinin irdelenmesi. *Adıyaman Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (15), 185-203.
- Eser, G. (2007). *Etik iklim ve yöneticiye güvenin örgüte bağlılığa etkisi* (Yüksek lisans tezi, RA Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İşletme Anabilim Dalı, Yönetim ve Organizasyon Bilim Dalı). İstanbul.
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2010). *SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference* (10th ed.). Pearson.
- Göksoy, Ş. (2022). *Ortaokul öğretmenlerinin yaşam boyu öğrenme eğilimleri ile mesleki etik davranışları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* (Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi). Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi, Burdur.
- Gözütok, F. D. (1999). Öğretmenlerin etik davranışları. *Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Fakültesi Dergisi*, 32(1), 83–99.
- Grant, A. M. (2002). *The effectiveness of teaching moral development on the ethical decisions of first and second grade children* (Unpublished master's thesis). Rowan University.
- Gümüseli, A. İ. (2006). Okul kültürü ve liderlik. *Artı Eğitim Dergisi*, 14.
- Harris, H. (1999). Courage as a management virtue. *Business and Professional Ethics Journal*, 18(3–4), 27–46. <https://doi.org/10.5840/bpej1999183/416>

- Ilgaz, S., & Bilgili, T. (2006). Eğitim ve öğretimde etik. *Atatürk Üniversitesi Kazım Karabekir Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 14, 199–210.
- İskender, H. (2024). *Öğretmenlerin etik davranışları ile örgütsel bağlılık arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* (Yüksek lisans tezi). Recep Tayyip Erdoğan Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü.
- Joseph, P. B., & Efron, S. (1993). Moral choices/moral conflicts: Teachers' self-perceptions. *Journal of Moral Education*, 22(3), 201–220.
- Kahveci, A. (2019). *Örgütsel erdemliliğin etik iklim ve psikolojik iyi oluşa etkisi* [Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Selçuk Üniversitesi.
- Kılıç, M. Y. (2019). Okullarda yöneticinin sağladığı etik iklimin, örgütsel bağlılık ve öğretmen performansına etkisi. *Cumhuriyet Uluslararası Eğitim Dergisi*, 8(3), 807–836.
- Kidder, R. M. (2005). Moral courage, digital distrust: Ethics in a troubled world. *Business and Society Review*, 110(4), 485–505.
- Klaassen, C. (2007). The moral role of teachers investigated: What did we learn? Paper presented at the 2007 Annual Convention of the American Educational Research Association, Chicago, IL.
- Klaassen, C., & Maslovaty, N. (2010). Teachers and normative perspectives in education: An introduction. In C. Klaassen & N. Maslovaty (Eds.), *Moral courage and the normative professionalism of teachers* (pp. 1–12). Sense Publishers.
- Korkmaz, Ş. D. (2025). *Hemşirelerin ahlaki cesaret düzeylerinin mesleki doyum ile ilişkisi* (Yüksek lisans tezi). KTO Karatay Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü.
- Kuçuradi, İ. (2003). *İnsan ve değerleri*. Türkiye Felsefe Kurumu Yayınları.
- Lachman, V. D. (2007). *Moral courage: A virtue in need of development?* *MedSurg Nursing*, 16(2), 131–133.
- Miller, W. I. (2000). *The mystery of courage*. Harvard University Press.
- Özen, F., & Durkan, E. (2016). Algılanan örgütsel etik iklim ile öğretmenlik meslek etiği arasındaki ilişki. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 22(4), 593–627.
- Pelit, E., & Güçer, E. (2006). Öğretmen adaylarının öğretmenlik mesleğiyle ilgili etik olmayan davranışlara ve öğretmenleri etik dışı davranışa yönelten faktörlere ilişkin algılamaları. *Gazi Üniversitesi Ticaret ve Turizm Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 2, 95–119.
- Peterson, C., & Seligman, M. E. P. (2004). *Character strengths and virtues: A handbook and classification*. Oxford University Press.
- Pianalto, M. (2012). Moral courage and facing others. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies*, 20(2), 165–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09672559.2012.668308>
- Reingold, R., & Baratz, L. (2020). Arab school principals in Israel—between conformity and moral courage. *Intercultural Education*, 31(1), 87–101. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14675986.2019.1685624>
- Sağnak, M. (2005). İlköğretim okullarında görevli yönetici ve öğretmenlerin örgütsel etik iklim türlerine ilişkin algı ve doyum düzeyleri. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research (EJER)*, (20), 115–130.
- Sarıdaş, G., & Yıldırım, Ö. (2019). Öğretmenler etik davranıyor mu? Öğretmenlerin meslektaşları hakkındaki algılarının incelenmesi. *Journal of Computer and Education Research*, 7(14), 621–641.
- Sekerka, L. E., & Bagozzi, R. P. (2007). Moral courage in the workplace: Moving to and from the desire and decision to act. *Business Ethics: A European Review*, 16(2), 132–149. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8608.2007.00484.x>
- Sekerka, L. E., & Godwin, L. (2010). Strengthening professional moral courage: A balanced approach to ethics training. *Training & Management Development Methods*, 24(4), 563.
- Sekerka, L. E., & Zolin, R. (2005). Professional courage in the military: Regulation fit and establishing moral intent. *Business & Professional Ethics Journal*, 24(4), 27–50.

- Sekerka, L. E., Bagozzi, R. P., & Charnigo, R. (2009). *Facing ethical challenges in the workplace: Conceptualizing and measuring professional moral courage*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 89(4), 565–579. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-008-0017-5>
- Serrat, O. (2017). Moral courage in organizations. In *Knowledge solutions: Tools, methods, and approaches to drive organizational performance* (pp. 489–497). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-0983-9_55
- Sockett, H. (1993). *The moral base for teacher professionalism*. Teachers College Press.
- Starratt, R. J. (2004). *Ethical leadership*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Steinberg, M. P., & Garrett, R. (2016). Classroom composition and measured teacher performance: What do teacher observation scores really measure? *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 38(2), 293–317. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0162373715616249>
- Şahin, B., & Dündar, T. (2011). Sağlık sektöründe etik iklim ve yıldırma (mobbing) davranışları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. *Ankara Üniversitesi SBF Dergisi*, 66(01), 129–159.
- Şener, E. B. (2025). *The relationship between ethical leadership and moral courage: The mediating role of ethical climate and the moderating role of moral disengagement* (Yüksek lisans tezi). Marmara Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Şentürk, C. (2009). Öğretmenlik mesleğinde etik. *Bilim ve Aklın Aydınlığında Eğitim*, 10(111), 25–29.
- Şişman, M. (2013). *Eğitim bilimine giriş*. Pegem Akademi.
- Taraz, Z., Loghmani, L., Abbaszadeh, A., Ahmadi, F., Safavibiat, Z., & Borhani, F. (2019). The relationship between ethical climate of hospital and moral courage of nursing staff. *Electronic Journal of General Medicine*, 16(2).
- Toprakçı, E., Bozpolat, E., & Buldur, S. (2010). Öğretmen davranışlarının kamu meslek etiği ilkelerine uygunluğu. *E-International Journal of Educational Research*, 1(2), 35–50.
- Uğurlu, C. T. (2009). *İlköğretim okulu öğretmenlerinin örgütsel bağlılık düzeylerine yöneticilerinin etik liderlik ve örgütsel adalet davranışlarının etkisi* (Doktora tezi). İnönü Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Malatya.
- Victor, B., & Cullen, J. B. (1988). The organizational bases of ethical work climates. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 33(1), 101–125. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392857>
- Weeks, W. A., Loe, T. W., Chonko, L. B., & Wakefield, K. (2004). The effect of perceived ethical climate on the search for sales force excellence. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 24(3), 199–214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08853134.2004.10749031>
- Wei, X. (2018). The influence of school ethical climate on teachers' organizational citizenship behavior: The mediating effect of work ethic. *Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Education and Cognition, Behavior, Neuroscience (ICECBN 2018)*.
- Wimbush, J. C., & Shepard, J. M. (1994). Toward an understanding of ethical climate: Its relationship to ethical behavior and supervisory influence. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 13(8), 637–647. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00871811>
- Yağmur, A. (2013). *Etik liderliğin ve etik iklimin etik dışı davranışlara etkisi: Ampirik bir çalışma* (Yüksek lisans tezi). Gebze Yüksek Teknoloji Enstitüsü, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Yakar, A. G. (2024). *Öğretmenlerin kapsayıcı eğitime ilişkin tutumları ile etik davranışları arasındaki ilişki* (Yüksek lisans tezi). Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü.
- Yavuz, A. (2022). *Devlet okullarında yönetici ve öğretmenlerce algılanan örgütsel etik iklim ile örgütsel adalet ilişkisi* [Yüksek lisans tezi]. Harran Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Eğitim Bilimleri Ana Bilim Dalı, Eğitim Yönetimi. Şanlıurfa.
- Yeşil, S., Mavi, Y., & Ceylan, S. (2017). Etik iklim algısı ve bireysel sonuçlar üzerine etkileri. *Dumlupınar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, (51), 19–38.
- Yıldırım, N. (2018). Geleceğin dünyasında idealist öğretmenlik. Emel Tüzel (Ed.), *22.Yüzyılda Eğitim içinde* (s.111-123). Ankara: Pegem Akademi.

Yollu, S. (2023). *Okul yöneticilerinin otantik liderlik davranışları ile öğretmenlerin pozitif psikolojik sermaye ve ahlaki cesaret davranışları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* (Doktora tezi). Gazi Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü.

Yollu, S., Yumuşak, H., & Korkmaz, M. (2024). Adaptation of the professional moral courage scale to Turkish culture: A validity and reliability study. *Uluslararası Türk Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 12(1), 221–254. <https://doi.org/10.46778/goputeb.1341919>

Zembylas, M. (2024). Can schools teach moral and civil courage? *Journal of Moral Education*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057240.2024.2326057>